

Education

September 2023

The **Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport** is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region’s economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda is monitored by the project POLICY ANSWERS, and the wider context and progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this brief report card, you find a first outline of the baseline data collected during 2022 and the first months of 2023.

In terms of Education, the monitoring focuses, on the one hand, on the context indicator “Learning-adjusted schooling years” and, on the other hand, on a variety of achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see on the backside of this document).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Learning-adjusted schooling years (in absolute numbers)

Source

World Bank <https://tinyurl.com/sourceindicator> (accessed 22 January 2023).

More information on the indicator: <https://tinyurl.com/moreaboutind>

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Priority

Supporting innovative practices in education and training

Regional Indicators

Western Balkans Steering Platform meetings on Education and Training	
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Legend: Information not available

WB Economy Indicators

Performance of the WB economy: information not provided

	Integration & stronger participation in EU programmes and initiatives			Fostered capacity building for R&I, education and VET	
	Supporting the implementation of Acquis				
Albania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Supporting document issued - No projects & missions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meetings not organised, commitments not undertaken 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Promotion & info meetings held, research mobilities undertaken 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Conducted 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No awareness / capacity building events, no publications
Bosnia and Herzegovina	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Supporting document issued, TAIEX mission organised - Information on projects not provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + A number of commitments undertaken/achieved - Information on meetings and participants not provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Promotion & info meetings held, research mobility undertaken 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Conducted 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information not provided
Kosovo*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information not provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + A number of commitments undertaken/achieved - Information on meetings and participants not provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promotion & info meeting held, information on WB-EU research mobilities not provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Conducted 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Considerable number of participants, number of events not specified - No publications
Montenegro	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No projects, missions or guidelines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information not provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information not provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Conducted 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Several events organised, number of participants not specified - No publications
North Macedonia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Twinning project in place - No TA projects or missions - Information on supporting documents not provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + A number of meetings organised - Information on participants and commitments not provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Promotion & info meetings held, research mobilities undertaken 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Conducted 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information not provided
Serbia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Supporting documents issued - No projects & missions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + A number of commitments undertaken/achieved - Information on meetings and participants not provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Promotion & info meetings held, research mobilities undertaken 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Conducted 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + A number of events with considerable number of participants organised - Information on number of publications not provided

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